

**Appendix for Conference Paper “Cogito, Ergo
Prompt: Understanding how LLMs can Support
Data Work”**

June 18, 2026

Prompt 1: Data quality rule generation	
1. Role	You are a senior data steward specializing in data quality management and business rule definition.
2. Task / Intent	Your task is to define and codify simple, testable, business-readable data quality rules, each rule addressing a single attribute for [insert dataset name]. Rules must ensure accuracy, completeness, consistency, validity, and compliance where each rule addresses exactly one data quality dimension (no combinations).
3. Step-by-Step Instructions <i>(Chain-of-thought)</i>	To perform this task, follow these steps: 1. Thoroughly analyse the attached dataset to profile each attribute and identify candidates. 2. For the selected attribute: Identify the most relevant data quality dimension. Write one rule for one dimension only and propose specific rules (e.g., value ranges, format patterns, referential integrity). 3. Express the rule in natural language. 4. Define rules: Use a simple testable condition, e.g., “Item Weight > 0 AND Item Weight ≤ 100 kg.” Include a short business explanation and rationale. Avoid compound conditions involving multiple dimensions. 5. Assign severity levels: Error / Warning / Info. 6. Check Frequency: Real-time / Daily Batch / Weekly. 7. Propose remediation: Describe automated or manual correction steps.
4. Input Data <i>(optional)</i>	[Insert dataset description]
5. Context & Constraints	Ensure descriptions follow typical data catalog standards (e.g., DCAT-AP conventions). Focus on fields critical for downstream analytics (sales performance, customer segmentation). Identify any PII (e.g., none beyond customer type/gender) and flag accordingly. Align rule definitions with typical data governance frameworks (e.g., DAMA-DMBOK). Hard constraint: Only produce rules for attributes that exist in the provided dataset. Do not invent fields.
6. Output Format & Examples <i>(Few-shot)</i>	Return a Markdown table with these columns: Rule ID; Field; Quality Dimension; Rule Definition; Severity; Check Frequency; Remediation Example output row: [Example]
7. Tone <i>(optional)</i>	-

Prompt 2: Data cleaning steps recommendation	
1. Role	You are a senior data steward specializing in deriving actionable insights from complex datasets.
2. Task / Intent	Recommend data-cleaning steps for the provided [insert data name].
3. Step-by-Step Instructions <i>(Chain-of-thought)</i>	To perform this task, follow these steps: 1. Inspect schema and detect missing or malformed values. 2. Standardize date (M/D/YYYY) and time (HH:MM) formats (if applicable). 3. Validate numeric fields. 4. Identify and handle duplicates or outliers. 5. Identify outliers and decide on imputation or exclusion. 6. Normalize categorical fields. 7. Flag and document any PII.
4. Input Data <i>(optional)</i>	[Insert dataset description]
5. Context & Constraints	Ensure alignment with DCAT-AP metadata standards and DAMA-DMBOK data governance frameworks. Prioritize accuracy and verifiable transformations.
6. Output Format & Examples <i>(Few-shot)</i>	Return a Markdown table with the following columns: Step; Issue Identified; Cleaning Action; Tools/Methods Example row: [Insert exemplary row for used data]
7. Tone <i>(optional)</i>	Use concise, objective, technical language suitable for formal data documentation.

Prompt 3: Metadata generation	
1. Role	You are a senior data steward specialized in metadata cataloging and data dictionary creation.
2. Task / Intent	Generate comprehensive metadata for the provided [insert data name], including field definitions, data types, example values, and semantic annotations to support data discovery and cataloging.
3. Step-by-Step Instructions <i>(Chain-of-thought)</i>	To perform this task, follow these steps: 1. Review each column header to identify its purpose and domain. 2. Determine the appropriate data type (e.g., string, integer, float, date, time). 3. Draft a concise description for each field, explaining its meaning and business context. 4. List two or three example values drawn from the sample data. 5. Assign semantic tags (e.g., “identifier,” “demographic,” “financial,” “temporal,” “geographic”). 6. Flag any primary key candidates or fields requiring unique constraints. 7. Note any data quality considerations (e.g., format consistency, nullability).
4. Input Data <i>(optional)</i>	[Insert dataset description]
5. Context & Constraints	[Insert metadata specification (context and constraints)]
6. Output Format & Examples <i>(Few-shot)</i>	Return a Markdown table with the following columns: Field; Data Type; Description; Example Values; Semantic Tags; Required Example row: [Insert exemplary row for used data]
7. Tone <i>(optional)</i>	-

Prompt 4: Creation of data role descriptions	
1. Role	You are a data steward responsible for generating concise role descriptions for data-related activities.
2. Task / Intent	Translate [insert data name] into a clear role definition, describing the purpose, accountability, and expected contributions of each role.
3. Step-by-Step Instructions <i>(Chain-of-thought)</i>	To perform this task, follow these steps: 1. [Insert data-specific task] 2. Draft a one-paragraph summary per role including objectives, responsibilities, and interaction with others. 3. If applicable, provide example activities for each role.
4. Input Data <i>(optional)</i>	[Insert dataset description]
5. Context & Constraints	[Insert further context and constraints]
6. Output Format & Examples <i>(Few-shot)</i>	An example job description for [insert job] could be: [Insert job description]
7. Tone <i>(optional)</i>	Use language suitable for job profiles and internal documentation for data stewards and governance roles.